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**COSMETICS AND GODDESSES:
THE WELLSTED COLLECTION AT THE BRITISH MUSEUM¹**

The Wellsted collection at the British Museum consists of a selection of small pottery vessels and a sculpture of a Nāga discovered by T. A. Wellsted at Mansar in the Deccan.² Hans Bakker has drawn attention to these pieces and explored their importance for the history of the Vākāṭaka kingdom and its archaeology. His proposal that the Nāga figure was part of a funereal monument to Prabhāvatīguptā – herself of Nāga descent – was first mooted at a conference held

Figure 1. Stone palette, decorated with animals and floral scrolls, fifth century. From Nāgpur district. *British Museum Asia* 1976. 4-5. 1 Presented by T. A. Wellsted.

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² T. A. Wellsted, 'Notes on the Vakatakas of the Central Provinces and Berar and their Country, 4th to 8th Century AD', *Journal and Proceedings of the Asiatic Society of Bengal, New Series*, 29 (1933): 159-66. *Museum numbers Asia* 1930.10-7.1-25.

at the British Museum in 2005.³ A few years later, in the course of the seminar reported in this volume, the participants toured the Museum's Asian gallery and noticed that a small stone palette on exhibition had entered the collections from Wellsted (figure 1). Records show that this piece did not come with the excavated items in 1930, but was gifted by Wellsted to the Department of Oriental Antiquities in 1976. At the same time, Wellsted donated a small female figure of the type generally termed Lajjā Gaurī (figures 4–5). Both pieces have no clear provenance. All that is recorded is that they came from Nāgpur district in Maharashtra. My purpose here is to comment on these items and to explore, more generally, some of the problems connected with them. The pieces are very different in appearance, but share one thing: we know next to nothing about their meaning and purpose. Both are useful reminders of what we are apt to forget, namely, that our knowledge of early Hindu India under the Vākāṭakas and Guptas is still in its infancy.

Figure 2. Ivory plaque showing a girl looking in a mirror, *circa* eighth century. From Brāhminābād, Sind. *British Museum, Asia 1857. 11-18. 8 Collection of A. F. Bellasis*

Figure 3. Circular palette with eight compartments and a coupe in the centre, *circa* third century. From North West Frontier Province. *British Museum, Asia 1939. 1-19. 14 Presented by H H R Deane*

Stone Palette

The stone palette depicted above in figure 1 originally had five circular compartments edged with lotus petals. Between the circular compartments are a variety of creatures and delicately carved floral scrolls. The creatures that remain are a makara, at the top, a horse and some sort of aquatic animal, perhaps a tortoise. The scroll work belongs to a type prevalent in the fifth century with

³ Hans T. Bakker, 'A Funerary Monument to Prabhāvatīguptā?' in *Religion and Art: New Issues in Indian Iconography*, edited by Claudine, (London, 2007): 81–91.

parallels, for example, in the dated decoration on the doorways at Udayagiri (early fifth century) and the halos of Buddha images from Mathurā and Sārnāth (mid- to late fifth century). There is not much evidence otherwise, the only pointer to a fifth-century date being that similar items were found at or near archaeological sites of the Vākāṭaka period.

As far as function goes, there is no direct evidence but the generally accepted view that they are trays for cosmetics may be accepted as a starting point. There is an established convention in the visual culture of India for ladies attending to their appearance, applying make-up and looking in mirrors. Aside from the famous ivory from Begram, a post-Vākāṭaka example in this genre, dating probably to the eighth century, comes from the site of Brāhminābād in Sind where it was excavated in the mid-nineteenth century by A. F. Bellasis (figure 2).⁴ The point is that if there were well-developed conventions for representing young ladies concerned with their beauty, then the apparatus for make-up, perfume and the like should also have been well developed. Toilet trays are, of course, known in considerable numbers from ancient Gandhāra, the key study being that of Henri Francfort.⁵ The items from the north-west are invariably circular and typically have only one compartment below figures of griffins, couples and the like. Some, however, have multiple compartments and these presage Vākāṭaka examples. One example in the British Museum may be taken as representative of these more complex types (figure 3). It is noteworthy that the individual compartments are edged with lotus flowers as in the Vākāṭaka palette.

The Goddess known as Lajjā Gaurī

The second item from the Wellsted collection is a small stone figurine of a goddess (figure 4–5). The image belongs to a widespread type which is striking and quickly described: the goddess is shown recumbent with her legs splayed to reveal her private parts; in lieu of a head, most depictions show a lotus flower and other vegetal motifs. The most developed and perhaps most famous example of this type comes from Bādāmi (figure 6). The key work on this goddess was written by C. Bolon and published in 1992. The goddess has usually been referred to as Lajjā Gaurī since that time due to the title of Bolon's book.⁶ The name is a modern one, more or less, the word *lajjā* coming from Kannada in which language *lajjābhāva* means 'modesty' or 'pudency'. The opposite, *nirlajjā*, means 'procacious' or 'abashless'. She is, therefore, a form of the goddess Gaurī known, somewhat curiously, for her modesty. In the remainder of this article I would like to explore the iconography of this deity and the methodological problems that her iconography raises.

Many technical and sacred texts contain iconographic information and devote substantial space to recording the gestures, attributes and proportions of divine

⁴ A. F. Bellasis, *An Account of the Ancient and Ruined City of Brahminabad, in Sind* (Bombay, 1856).

⁵ Henri-Paul Francfort, *Les palettes du Gandhāra* (Paris, 1979).

⁶ C. Bolon, *Forms of the Goddess Lajjā Gaurī in Indian Art* (University Park, PA, 1992).

Figures 4-5. Stone tablet with a figure of squatting goddess; front face and reverse. 6.6 cm x 7.60 cm. Probably 4th-5th century. *British Museum, Asia 1976. 4-5. 2 Presented by T. A. Wellsted.*

Figure 6. Squatting goddess, circa eighth century. From Bādāmi. *Archaeological Museum, B d mi.*

and semi-divine images. The publication of this literature, at times with instructive commentary, is well advanced in India, and some of this information has been incorporated into handbooks on iconography.⁷ This type of scholarship, tending to the descriptive rather than the interpretive, focuses on forms preserved in the literary record and thus still canonical in the strictest sense. An obvious example is Viṣṇu in his supernal form Viśvarūpa. Students of Indology will need no introduction to the Bhagavad Gītā and the stunning theophany celebrated in its eleventh chapter. Similar texts praising Śiva and the goddess could be cited. Such examples form part of what has been called the ‘great tradition’ of Hinduism; the images are recognisable and are, in many cases, still produced in sculpture, painting, and popular prints. Some deities, however, have fallen from favour and their

forms are no longer made or worshipped. These deities have tended to disappear from literary accounts, though fossilised or incidental references are occasionally preserved. Certainly, the best-known instance of this phenomenon is provided by early Buddhist art in north India. Although the apparent worship of trees and other objects shown in the early reliefs seemed baffling when first examined in the nineteenth century, a study of inscriptions and Buddhist texts led to a

⁷ The best-known classics are perhaps T. A. Gopinatha Rao, *Elements of Hindu Iconography* (Madras, 1914–16) and J. N. Banerjea, *The Development of Hindu Iconography*, 2nd ed. (Calcutta, 1956); more recent material is cited in the useful bibliography provided by S. Huntington, *The Art of Ancient India* (New York, 1985): 676–82. Aside from editions of the Purāṇa texts, etc., we might mention, as examples of śilpaśāstra, *Dīpārṇava*, ed. Prabhasankar O. Sompura (Palitana, 1960) and *Kṣīrārṇava*, ed. Prabhasankar O. Sompura (Ahmedabad, 1967), both with Gujarati translation, the second with Hindi also.

Figure 7. Copper plate charter, *circa* fifth century. From Kashmir Smast, NWFP, Pakistan. Private Collection. Photography courtesy Dr M. Nasim Khan.

remarkably thorough understanding of this sculpture and its iconographic peculiarities. This approach, which we might describe as an ‘archaeology of interpretation’, was pioneered by Ananda Coomaraswamy and has been carried forward by such scholars as Moti Chandra and V. S. Agrawala.⁸ What is significantly different with Lajjā Gaurī is that she seems, at first glance, to lack textual or epigraphic documentation.

The surprisingly wide distribution and large number of these goddesses indicate that Lajjā Gaurī was not a minor deity but part of an important and widespread cult. In addition to the some 120 examples in Bolon’s book, a cache of items has been found in Kashmir Smast, a cave in Pakistan. This included an invaluable copper-plate (figure 7) recording a perpetual endowment.⁹ All these finds are significant because they show the degree to which Hinduism, despite many continuities, has changed over the last millennium. Lajja Gaurī was worshipped in many parts of the country, enjoying special favor in the Deccan. It is curious that no images have been found in eastern India, but examples may yet be discovered. Only one example, at Alampur, remains in situ in a temple sanctum.¹⁰ Many examples are small or fragmentary, like the sculpture in the British Museum.

The surviving images can be divided typologically into four basic types: 1) a form with a pot-like body and splayed legs on each side; lotus flowers and plant sprays issue from the pot’s mouth; 2) a form with a pot-like body that includes shoulders and breasts; the floral and vegetal devices in this type are placed where the head might be expected; 3) a form in which arms have been added but which retains a lotus flower in lieu of a head; 4) a completely anthropomorphic form with all four

⁸ As prime examples of this approach see Coomaraswamy, ‘Indian Architectural Terms’, *JAOS* 48 (1928): 250–75 and ‘The Buddha’s cūḍa, Hair, uṣṇīṣa and Crown,’ *JRAS* (1928): 815–41. An exemplary work by Agrawala is *The Deeds of Harsha; being a Cultural Study of Bāṇa’s Harshacarita* (Varanasi, 1969).

⁹ M. Nasim Khan, ‘Lajja Gauri Seals and Related Antiquities from Kashmir Smast, Gandhara’, *South Asian Studies* 18 (2002): 83–90; H. Falk, ‘A Copper Plate Donation Record and Some Seals from the Kashmir Smast’, *Beiträge zur Allgemeinen und Vergleichenden Archäologie* 23 (2003): 1–19.

¹⁰ Bolon, *op. cit.*, figure 46.

limbs and a head. The first type is the most archaic in typological terms and shows that the womb was equated with the pūrṇakumbha or pot of plenty. This indicates that the goddess was an image of fertility and the source of life. The four types appeared concomitantly and do not, therefore, constitute a temporal sequence. The multi-figured plaques, all fifth century or later, help determine that the cultic associations of the goddess were consistently Śaiva.

There has been a desultory treatment of literary references that might help explain this goddess and put her in some kind of religious and historical context. Stella Kramrisch was the first to propose that Lajjā Gaurī could be equated with Aditi uttānapad.¹¹ To support this she cited passages in the Vājasaneyā Saṃhitā and Ṛgveda (without providing texts), revealing in a footnote that it was actually to Sanskritist W. Norman Brown who first identified the image as 'uttānapad'. Bolon agreed that the word uttānapad 'exactly describes this image' and mentions some of the early texts where the term occurs.¹² A cursory check shows, however, that these references simply repeat what is found in M. Monier-Williams, Sanskrit-English Dictionary (Oxford, 1899), s.v. Bolon does not cite the relevant discussion in K. F. Geldner, *Der Rigveda*, 3 vols. (Gottingen, 1923), 3: 250–51. While it may well be that these references shed no direct light on the iconography, the assertion (Bolon, op. cit., p. 8) that there are no texts to explain the images cannot be accepted until all the occurrences are studied with care. For example, Sāyaṇa's commentary on Ṛgveda 10: 72: 4 states: bhūḥ uttānapadaḥ vṛkṣāt jajñe.¹³ Why Sāyaṇa has introduced vṛkṣāt ('from a tree') is not immediately clear – at least to me – but this would seem to have some bearing on the subject considering the vegetal associations of the goddess. There is, in any event, a basic need to explore the texts in a systematic manner.

A closely related question, and one of considerable theoretical and historical importance, centres on the identification of Lajjā Gaurī with Aditi.¹⁴ Given that this goddess was understood, at least in part, as Aditi and can be traced to Vedic texts, I find it difficult to follow why Lajjā Gaurī should be considered some sort of rustic goddess of the village who came to be absorbed into the pantheon of Hinduism.¹⁵ How the Vedic deities find their place in Hinduism is indeed most interesting and worthy of exploration, but the work of Eschmann et al. on the cult of Jagannātha, which is frequently used as a model in circumstance of this kind, is not especially compelling.¹⁶ The process of 'Sanskritization' is another handy device used to explain away just about anything that seems inexplicable. This

¹¹ Kramrisch, 'An Image of Aditi-Uttānapad', *Artibus Asiae* 19 (1956): 259–70.

¹² Bolon., op. cit., p. 6.

¹³ N. S. Sontakke and C. G. Kashikar, eds., *Ṛgveda-saṃhitā with the commentary of Sāyaṇācārya*, 2nd ed., 5 vols. (Poona, 1983), 4: 537–38.

¹⁴ Bolon, op. cit., p. 65.

¹⁵ Bolon, op. cit., p. 68.

¹⁶ A. Eschmann, H. Kulke, and G. C. Tripathi, eds., *The Cult of Jagannātha and the Regional Traditions of Orissa* (New Delhi, 1978).

means, in essence, that if we don't know where it came from, it must have come out of the jungle or the gurgling socio-religious plasma of early India whence it was incorporated into the higher tradition. It may have happened like that sometimes, but a more useful and fruitful angle, in my view, would be an exploration of the literatures of the Yajurveda (see Table 1).

Y A J U R V E D A						
Recension	Black - Kṛṣṇa				White - Śukla	
School	Kapiṣṭhala Kaṭha	Caraka Kaṭha	Maitrāyaṇīya	Taittirīyaka	Vājasaneyin	
					Mādhyandina	Kāṇva
Samhitā	Kapiṣṭhalakaṭha	Kāṭhaka	Maitrāyaṇīya	Taittirīya samhitā	Mādhyandina samhitā	Kāṇva samhitā
Brāhmaṇa	samhitā	samhitā	samhitā	& brāhmaṇa	Śatapatha brāhmaṇa	
Āraṇyaka				Taittirīya āraṇyaka	Bṛhad āraṇyaka	
Upaniṣad		Kaṭha upaniṣad	Maitrāyaṇīya upaniṣad	Taittirīya Śvetāśvatara upaniṣads	Bṛhadāraṇyaka upaniṣad Īśa upaniṣad	
Śrauta-sūtra		Yajña śrautasūtra	Mānava śrautasūtra Vārāha śrautasūtra	Baudhāyana Bhāradvāja Āpastamba Hiraṇyakeśin Vādhūla Vaikhānasa śrautasūtra-s	Kātyāyana śrautasūtra	
Gṛhya-sūtra		Laugākṣi gṛhyasūtra	Mānava gṛhyasūtra Vārāha gṛhyasūtra	Baudhāyana Bhāradvāja Āpastamba Hiraṇyakeśin Vādhūla Vaikhānasa gṛhyasūtra-s	Pāraskara gṛhyasūtra	
Śulva-sūtra		Laugākṣi śulvasūtra	Mānava śulvasūtra	Baudhāyana Āpastamba śulvasūtra	Kātyāyana śulvasūtra	
Dharma-sūtra		Vaiṣṇava dharmasūtra =Viṣṇusmṛti	Hārīta dharmasūtra Mānava dharmasāstra	Baudhāyana Āpastamba Hiraṇyakeśin Vaikhānasa dharmasūtra	Yājñavalkyasmṛti	

Table 1. Overview of the schools of the Yajurveda and their primary texts.

Especially worthy of attention are the copper-plate charters of the Vākāṭakas which show that they granted land and revenue to the Taittirīya and Vājasaneyya schools. This means that the texts of these schools were known and recited in the Vākāṭaka realm. Within this corpora are Upaniṣads that are generally regarded as the first documents of the Maheśvara faith, i.e. the Śvetāśvatara Upaniṣad and Īśa Upaniṣad. Now given that Aditi uttānapad was known to the Vājasaneyya and that Lajjā Gaurī, when shown with other figures, is part of the Śaiva pantheon, I suspect that it is in this literature, its dependents and commentaries that we are likely to find some kind of understanding of our goddess and the religious environment in which she flourished under the Vākāṭakas and their successors. Such an investigation will have to be combined an awareness of archaeological material. The many tablets of Viṣṇu's feet to which Hans Bakker has drawn

attention, point to a large and more important royal cult.¹⁷ The numerous figures of Lajjā Gaurī very likely to do the same. This possibility highlights the point made at the beginning of this essay, i.e. that our knowledge of early Hinduism under the Vākāṭakas and Guptas is still in its infancy.

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¹⁷ Bakker, 'The Footprints of the Lord', in *Devotion Divine: Bhakti Traditions from the Regions of India, Studies in Honour of Charlotte Vaudeville* (Groningen and Paris, 1991): 20–37